

N management for late transplanting in northwestern India

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Transplanting in this region often is delayed to the end of Jul when monsoon rains are late. Different N rates and time of application are necessary in this situation.

We studied 3 rates of N (90, 120, and 150 kg/ha) applied in 4 ways in a split-plot design with 3 replications.

Soil of the experimental field was clay loam with 210 kg available N, 20.5 kg available P, and 225 kg available K/ha, EC 0.21 dS/m, 0.40% organic C, CEC 12.1 meq/100 g soil, and pH 7.8. P-K-Zn was applied at 26-50-6 kg/ha.

Seedlings of PR106 (60-d-old) and Pusa 33 (30-d-old) were transplanted 20 Jul in 1983 and 1984.

Effect of N rate on grain and straw yields of late-planted wet season rice. Kaul, India, 1983-84.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)			Straw yield (t/ha)		
	1983	1984	Mean	1983	1984	Mean
Variety						
PR 106	5.8	4.6	5.2	1.7	6.0	6.8
Pusa 33	5.2	4.3	4.7	5.1	4.6	4.9
LSD (0.05)	0.3	0.1	—	0.9	0.2	—
N rate (kg/ha)						
90	4.9	4.0	4.4	5.4	5.0	5.3
120	5.7	4.4	5.0	6.3	5.3	5.8
150	6.2	4.8	5.5	6.9	5.5	6.2
LSD (0.05)	0.3	0.3	—	0.4	0.1	—
Application method ^a						
All basal	5.2	—	5.2	6.2	—	6.2
½ basal + ½ 21 DT	5.5	4.2	4.8	6.8	5.6	6.2
½ basal + ¼ 21 DT + ¼ 42 DT	5.6	4.6	5.1	6.6	5.3	5.9
1/3 basal + 1/3 21 DT + 1/3 42 DT	5.5	4.5	5.0	6.0	5.0	5.5
LSD (0.05)	0.1	0.1	—	0.4	0.1	—

^aDT = days after transplanting.

Duration was 147 d for PR106 and 113 d for Pusa 33 in 1983, and 148 d for PR106 and 115 d for Pusa 33 in 1984. PR106 had higher yields than Pusa 33 in

both years (see table). Yield increased significantly up to 150 kg N/ha. Split N application was superior to basal application. □

Direct and residual effects of biogas residue application with nitrogen on rice yield

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Organic residues from biogas plants are rich sources of N. We studied direct and residual effects of biogas residue with N on rice yields of two rice - rice cropping sequences 1984-85 and 1985-86. The second wet season trial was laid out at a different site, but very close to the first trial site. Soil of the experimental sites was sandy loam (Haplaquept) with pH 5.3, 0.77% organic matter, CEC 11 meq/100 g soil, and 260-10-165 kg available N-P-K/ha.

Treatments were with and without biogas residue and 20, 40, and 60 kg N as urea/ha distributed equally at 1, 2, or 3 growth stages, in a randomized block design replicated 3 times. The biogas residue containing 1.11% N, 0.174% P,

Direct and residual effect of biogas residue fertilizer with different levels of urea on rice yield. Bhubaneswar, India, 1984-86.

t/ha	Treatment			Grain yield (t/ha)					
	BGR ^a + N application (kg/ha)			Direct effect (wet season)			Residual effect (dry season)		
	TP ^b	+ DT ^c	+ PI ^d	1984	1985	Mean	1984-85	1985-86	Mean
0	0	0	0	2.9	2.3	2.6	2.5	1.7	2.1
0	20	20	20	3.3	3.1	3.2	3.8	3.1	3.4
5	0	0	0	3.5	3.1	3.3	2.8	2.4	2.6
5	20	20	20	3.4	2.9	3.1	3.9	3.3	3.6
5	0	20	20	3.4	2.8	3.1	3.3	2.6	2.9
5	0	20	0	3.3	2.9	3.1	3.7	2.5	3.1
5	0	0	20	3.7	2.9	3.3	2.6	2.2	2.4
	CV (%)			1.3	9.4	7.7	18.4	21.2	18.8
	LSD (0.05)			0.3	0.4	0.3	0.7	0.5	0.4

^aBiogas residue applied in wet seasons only. ^bAt transplanting. ^cDays after transplanting. ^dPanicle initiation.

0.487% K, and 25% organic C on oven-dry basis was applied with 25% moisture at 5 t/ha to both wet season trials. The residual effect was studied in the following dry seasons. Both direct and residual trials also received 13 kg P and 25 kg K/ha, including the contribution from biogas residue.

Jajati was planted in the wet season, Daya in the dry season.

In the wet season, fresh biogas residue at 5 t/ha without supplemental N produced the maximum yield (see table)

In the dry season, 60 kg N/ha in equal applications in plots treated with biogas residue plus 60 kg N/ha in the wet season produced the maximum yield.

There was a large variation in grain yield among the plots.